

FEATURES OF TODAY'S UZBEK PHONETICS

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Abstract: Every language has its own phonetics. It has studied the specific features of the formation and pronunciation of sounds in this language, issues related to its classification, examines the relationship between pronunciation and writing, as well as features of stress and syllables. As phonetics studies the system of sounds of a language and any phenomena related to these sounds, it is connected with all areas of language, especially lexis and grammar.

Keywords: sounds of phenomena, pronunciation, phonetic phenomena, syllable and stress, phonetics, phonological units.

In phonetics, sounds in the language, their appearance and types, speech organs, their state of movement in sound production, speech apparatus, acoustic and articulatory properties of speech sounds, various phonetic phenomena that occur during speech, phonetic division of speech, sounds of phenomena such as communicative role and prosody are studied. So, phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the sound structure of the language in a broad sense. It checks for any events related to sounds. For this reason, it is wrong to consider it as a department that checks only the sound system of the language. Phonetics also studies such problems as the change and change of sounds, literary pronunciation standards, rules of correct pronunciation, syllable and stress, and its types. Therefore, it is impossible to successfully work on the rules of orthography and grammar (morphology and syntax), which are related to correct pronunciation, without having the necessary knowledge of phonetics. At the same time, the study of phonetics greatly helps to master the rules of orthography (correct writing), orthoepy (correct pronunciation), and to distinguish between literary pronunciation and dialect pronunciation. . So, phonetics is directly related to such departments of linguistics as orthography, orthography, lexicology, grammar, dialectology.

Phonetics is closely related to physics (part of acoustics) and physiology. Phonetics relies on acoustics to study the auditory side of sounds, and physiology to study the aspects of pronunciation and production. In addition, it has constant connections with literary studies (such as syllabary, metric, and affective reading) and the social sciences. Speech sounds can be studied from different angles: from a historical point of view, from a comparative point of view, from the point of view of comparing the speech sounds of the modern Uzbek language and local dialects, by experimenting with speech sounds using different instruments, etc. Accordingly, phonetics is theoretically divided into general phonetics and specific phonetics, and in practical terms it is divided into several areas, such as historical phonetics, comparative phonetics, descriptive phonetics, and experimental phonetics. Historical phonetics studies the sound system of a given language in its historical development, that is, it examines the historical changes in the sound system in different periods of

language development, and the reasons for their change. Live conversational speech, the results obtained as a result of the study of related languages, written monuments belonging to different periods of language development are the source for historical phonetics. The gradual development of sounds is studied in connection with the history of the people who speak this language, and historical reasons are determined. For example, the Uzbek language now has two variants of the phoneme “lip” and “lip-tooth”. Historical phonetics explains the reasons for the origin of these signs in the phoneme as follows: the variant “lip” is a primary and ancient phoneme for the Uzbek language. Pure Uzbek and original Turkish words use the lip-lab variant of this sound. For example, hunting, water, field, melon, driving, pasture. Later, as a result of the increasing interaction of the Uzbek language with other languages, the lip-tooth variant of this phoneme appears. This variant can be found in words such as promise, farewell, screw, wagon, time, province, borrowed from other languages, in particular, from Arabic, Persian, and Russian languages. Written monuments created in different periods, oral speech materials characteristic of different groups and dialects serve as the main source for historical phonetics. Historical phonetics also uses material related to general phonetics, comparative phonetics, and phonetics of the present language. Comparative phonetics studies the sound system relationships of related languages. For example, the comparative phonetics of the Turkic languages, as well as the comparative phonetics of the Slavic languages. In this, the materials of several related languages or several dialects and dialects - vowels and consonants, phonetic changes, and so on - are studied on the basis of comparison. For example, the law of synchronism is violated in the modern Uzbek literary language, but it is fully preserved in other Turkic languages, as well as in some Uzbek dialects. On the basis of the comparative study of this material, it is possible to come to the conclusion that the phenomenon of synchronism was fully present in the Uzbek literary language. Comparative phonetics, on the one hand, can study the comparative phonetics of two languages belonging to the same family (for example, the comparative phonetics of Russian and German languages), and on the other hand, the comparative phonetics of two languages belonging to two families (for example, the comparative phonetics of the Uzbek and Russian languages). Comparative phonetics is based, on the one hand, on the materials of general and descriptive phonetics, and on the other hand, on the materials of historical phonetics.

A. Abduazizov phonetically divides speech into phrases (phrases), tact, syllables and sounds, like all previous authors. It differs from others in that it opposes these units to emic units that can be contrasted in a paradigmatic line: sound - phoneme, tact - tactema, syllable - syllabeme, etc. Also, he traditionally distinguishes between segmental units and suprasegmental units, and introduces accents and intonations into suprasegmental units. The upper segment uses the terms accent-accenteme, tone-intoneme to distinguish generality-specificity in units. The main criterion for separating emic units is the function of meaning differentiation. The terms syllabe (characteristic of Chinese, Japanese, and Korean languages), phoneme for sound, accenteme for accent, and intoneme for tone are used for a syllable with a specific meaning. Thus, a certain relationship is established between phonetic units (sound, syllable, stress, tone) and phonological units.

The writing of the Uzbek language is considered a sound writing, because the sound is represented by letters in the writing. 1st grade students should learn the following:

- a) we pronounce and hear the sound;
- b) we see, read and write letters;
- c) letter - a symbol of a sound expressed in writing.

Students often make a mistake by mixing the sound with the letter. In order to develop graphic skills in them, it is necessary to teach the following:

- 1) one consonant letter can represent two consonant sounds in writing;
- 2) the “j” sound in the words “jo’ja” and “jajji” (sonorous, explosive) and the j sound in the words “journal” and “vijdon” (sonorous, sliding) are represented by one letter j;
- 3) the third sonorous consonant sound (ng) in the words “tong”, wide is combined with two letters (ng)
- 4) letter combinations sh, ch also represent one sound (shamol, choy).

Knowing the world begins with studying its parts (fragments). In addition to being a separate object of analysis, each fragment submitted to the discussion is compared and contrasted with another similar object. Then its true value will be determined. In addition to having common features, the compared objects have unique properties that are not present in the other. This characteristic is the basis for distinguishing a certain unit from other similar units. And difference creates conflict. Linguistic units, in particular, phonological units, are united in the language system based on their common features, forming a phonological system, each member of the phonological system also has a sign of differentiation and enters into a conflicting relationship with other members of the system to which it belongs. The services of N.S. Trubetskoy are recognized in the coverage of these relations. N.S.Trubetskoy distinguished the distinguishing signs of phonological units at the phonological level and contrasted one unit with another based on these signs. As a result, unifying and differentiating signs of phonemes were determined, and the sign of differentiation was determined as the main criterion for the classification of phonemes. The concept of difference requires the concept of contradiction. N.S.Trubetskoy said that two things show a sign of mutual difference only when they contradict each other.

Similarly, only when the sign of sounds contradicts the sign of other similar sounds, its distinguishing (distinctive) function is manifested. N.S. Trubetskoi interprets the phonological system as a set of phonological oppositions that serve to differentiate lexical and grammatical meanings. He emphasizes that distinguishing signs play the main role in phonology. In the classification of phonological contradictions, the sign of their difference in meaning and lack of difference in meaning is important. According to this sign, phonological conflicts are divided into meaning-differentiating and non-meaning-differentiating conflicts. The first conflict is a phonologically important conflict, which, along with the material formation of morphemes and words, serves to differentiate their meanings. Therefore, any phoneme will necessarily be a member of a certain contrast. And any real pronounced sound will also have non-phonologically important features. Therefore, in order to determine the invariant-variant relationship in consonants, it is very important to distinguish their phonologically important and insignificant signs. That is why linguistic conflicts play an important role in the differentiation of language units. Consonant phonemes in the Uzbek language are also classified on the basis of three signs that are the basis for mutual contradiction - the place of articulation, the method of articulation, and the presence of voice and noise. According to the place of articulation, consonants are divided into guttural, tongue and lip consonants. These, in turn, have internal divisions. According to the method of articulation, consonants are divided into sliding, plosive and plosive (mixed). According to the participation of voice and noise, consonants are divided into three groups: sonorous, voiced and voiceless. For consonants in the phonological system of the Uzbek language, the above symbols are considered phonologically important and are the basis for their mutual differentiation.

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